

Literature Review on Customer Engagement of Millennials in Digital Marketing

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ABSTRACT

Purpose

This study aims to uncover consumer engagement research that has been undertaken since 2005 and to comprehend the numerous concepts and empirical investigations that have been conducted based on diverse theories. This report will also synthesize the study's numerous findings and suggest areas that have not been thoroughly investigated, allowing for future research. A rigorous assessment of the literature on the evolution of customer interaction should disclose the contributions and disagreements on the concepts created.

Methodology

Extensive data mining was conducted and out of a total of 810 papers, 149 scholarly papers published in top journals top publishers such as Emerald Insight, Elsevier, Taylor and Francis, SAGE, Springer. Papers with high citations were selected for final review.

Findings

Customer engagement has been identified as a critical component of marketing. However, there is no universal agreement on the concepts and dimensions of customer engagement, and both scholars and practitioners are working tirelessly to uncover a more precise aspects in order to design effective customer retention methods. Cognitive, emotional, social, and behavioral engagement characteristics are relatively well-aligned. Marketing relations theory and Service-Dominant (S-D) theories were determined to be the most commonly employed theories.

Research Limitations

The non-availability of many scholarly papers was a significant limitation. This shortcoming was largely overcome by obtaining working papers. Still, many papers were reviewed with their abstracts, which may have caused some errors in the findings. Many other important chapters, blogs, theses, and conference papers were not reviewed due to the limitation of the length of the paper, which may also lead to the loss of some important aspects of customer dimensions.

Contribution

Through this review paper, a large number of scholarly papers was made available as a single source reference. This paper expects to highlight the important research aspects of customer engagement.

Keywords: Customer Engagement, Consumer Engagement, Literature Review, Digital Media, Millennials

1. INTRODUCTION

Customer engagement is referred to as building, creating and meaningfully engaging the customer, thereby building a relationship (Brodie et al, 2013). Customer engagement has become an inevitable component in marketing to gain a competitive advantage (Van Doorn et al, 2010). Customer engagement leads to customer satisfaction, which leads to the loyalty of the customer, (Hollebeek, 2011a), apart from enhancing the firm's image and performance. A Gallop poll shows that an engaged customer is 37% more profitable than an unengaged customer.

Prior to 2005, the concept of customer engagement was not a serious subject of research. However, with the emergence of Web2.0, the interaction of customers through the internet started to popularize. As a consequence, one to-one interaction with companies started gaining momentum and the imperativeness of retaining customers through the company website started gaining momentum. Customer engagement attracted practitioners and scholars alike and Innumerable studies were conducted. As a result, many concepts were framed on the basis of many theories. Despite all these, the extant literature as of now reveals that there is no consensus on the concept dimensions of customer engagement. Hence, there is a dire need to unify the various concepts to explain it on a single platform. This has led to the much deeper research dimensions of customer engagement and a plethora of research papers were published since 2010, predominantly related

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to the behavioral and psychological dimensions of customer engagement (Verhoef et Al,2010), (Kumar et. Al ,2010), (Bowden, 2009), Brodie and Hollebeck, (2011), which opened further opportunities for research in this novel area.

With the advent of technology, customer retention has become imperative, thanks to the stiff competition among companies. In addition to this, highly advanced marketing technology has been revolutionizing digital marketing and social media has been a widely accepted platform to interact with customers. Hence, brand communities started forming, which further enhanced the need for retention and the research dimensionalities of customer engagement increased further. This has led to studies on the relationship between brands (Sprott,2009, Gamebetti et.al,(2012)) and firms (Gummurus et.al,(2012) with the customers. Many new terms, such as ' Online Brand Community (OBC),' Online Brand Engagement (OBE),' Virtual Brand Engagement (VBE) and Online Engagement Behavior (OBE) were formed and discussed. Technological innovations and web3.0 further elevated the essentiality of retaining customers, as social media turned out to be a platform that has been growing exponentially. Thus, marketers found social media as a conducive platform to strategize customer engagement.

This paper is to study the various concepts of customer engagement in marketing, evolved during the last years, to propose a research agenda, which would pave the way for further research. Since then, both academicians and practitioners are still struggling to reach a consensus on the conceptual frame work and its impact on customer engagement. A systematic review was conducted in this defense, with much literature published in top journals.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- a. To investigate the extant literature on Customer Engagement and understand the theories and conceptual models.
- b. To study the transformation of customer engagement parameters evolved during the last 17 years.
- c. To examine the relevance of customer engagement in the wake of fast-changing digital marketing technology.
- d. To understand the various determinants that affect Millennials customer engagement with a focus on digital marketing platforms.

To identify the suitable research gap in the research literature

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To investigate the literature, various publishers such as Emerald, SAGE, Taylor and Francis, Science Direct, Springer were searched through a front-end data base search software called 'Publish or Perish' and search engine Google Scholar. The search criteria for the selection of the years were 2005-2021, with various key words as follows :

- a. 'Customer Engagement' : 200
- b. 'Consumer Engagement' : 100
- c. 'Customer Engagement Behavior' : 100
- d. 'Consumer Engagement behavior' : 100
- e. 'Customer Engagement Digital Marketing' : 100
- f. 'Customer Engagement Martech' : 100
- g. 'Customer Engagement Millennials' : 100
- h. Other Relevant Literature prior to 2005 : 10

Total papers downloaded : 810

3.1 Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

The search result was sorted based on the citation nos. Table No. 1 shows the criteria applied in order to screen out the literature.

Table 1: Citation Criteria for exclusion

Years	Criteria Not Applied
2005–2008	Criteria Not Applied
2009-2010	Less than 100
2011	Less than 50
2012–2014	Less than 40
2015–2016	Less than 20
2017–2018	Less than 15
2019	Less than 8
2020-2021	Criteria Not Applied

The papers thus short listed were further subjected to screening based on the following criteria

- a. Duplication

- b. Less reputed journals/Predatory journals
- c. Books
- d. Blogs
- e. Other on research publications

Only reputed journals published by the top publishers such as Elsevier, Emerald Insights, SAGE, Taylor and Francis, Springer, McMillan and Wiley were mainly considered. However, a few other reputed journals were also considered considering the quality and relevancy of such papers. Except for a few articles, book chapters, editorial and literature review papers, all other papers were with high citations and of the leading researchers of this area of study.

After screening 810 papers, 461 such papers were removed from the search result. The second round of screening was based on the irrelevant literature. This was done through abstract reading and 152 such papers were removed. The remaining 187 papers were further scrutinized and quick reading conducted for fine relevancy and 48 papers were further removed to improve the quality of literature. Thus, a total of 149 scholarly papers with high citation index was selected for literature survey. The detailed screening analysis is given in Table 2. The details of the journals and publishers are given in Table 3.

Table 2 : Selection of Literature ,Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Selection of Journals (Years Selected - 2005 –2021)		Included	Nos	Excluded	Ist Screen (Nos)	IInd Screen (Nos)	Final Screen (Nos)
Keywords Selected	No. Literature Downloaded						
Customer Engagement	200	Journals by reputed publishers	128	Books	27		
Consumer Engagement	100	Editorial	5	Theses	6		
Customer Engagement Behavior	100	Book Chapters	2	Duplication, Blogs etc.	174		
Consumer Engagement Behavior	100	Literature Review	4	Less reputed Journals	151		
Customer Engagement Digital Marketing	100	Other Relevant paper (Old)	10	Less Citation	103		
Customer Engagement Martech	100			Irrelevant papers		152	48
Customer Engagement Millennials	100			Sub Total	461	152	48
Other relevant theories etc.	10						
Total	810	Final Selected Papers	149				

Table 3 : Journal Details of the literature and the publishers

Top Journal (Name)	Nos	Years	No. of Papers	Top Publishers	No	Type of Study/Literature	Nos
Journal of Business Research	7	2005	1	Elsevier	35	Conceptual	53
Journal of Interactive Marketing	6	2006	0	Emerald Insight	36	Empirical	78
Journal of Product and Brand Management	5	2007	0	Taylor and Francis	19	Others	18
Journal of Service Research	10	2008	1	SAGE	11		
Journal of Retailing and Consumer Service	6	2009 –2010	10	Wiley	2		
Journal of Academic Science and Marketing	4	2011	5	Mc Millan	2		
Procedia Social and Behavioral Science	6	2012-2014	38	Others	44		
Journal of Service Marketing	3	2015-2016	21				
European Journal of Marketing	3	2017–2018	31				
Industrial Marketing Management	3	2019	21				
Journal of Marketing Management	3	2020	9				
Market Intelligence and Planning	3	2021	2				
Others	90	Prior to 2005	10				
Total	149	Total	149	Total	149	Total	149

4. ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE

An analysis of selected literature has been conducted. The whole papers were sorted chronologically, starting in 2005. The analysis shows that prior to 2005, Customer Engagement as a topic did not receive due attention and no significant conceptual frame work was formed. The following analysis of selected papers depicts the transpiring journey (Islam, 2016) of customer engagement. Even though CE received prominent scholarly attention after 2005, the research in this area was too divergent and could not arrive at a consensus on the concepts, although the fact that practitioners and scholars have extensively contributed to the enrichment of CE and many empirical studies was conducted to validate the concepts.

The following analysis is divided into manner by the various researches were conducted in this field, such as Definition, Theoretical, Conceptual Framework, Dimensionalities, Antecedents and Consequences of CE.

4.1 Conceptual Frame Work and Theoretical Background

The conceptual framework of CE was mostly centered around the behavioral manifestations (Vandoorn,2010), which was termed as Customer Engagement behavior (CEB), psychological influence (Hollebeek 2011b, Brodie et.al 2011), Patterson et al (2016)etc.. Later, the focus was shifted to various other dimensions such as parameters on social media (Gummerus,et.al.,(2012), Wirtz et al. (2013), O'Brien (2010) etc.

4.2 Dimensionalities

While some authors conceptualized CE as a one-dimensional or two dimensional, some others have added more dimensions to it. Most of the studies were around behavioral, emotional, Cognitive and social dimensions

4.3 Definition of CE

In spite of various studies by many authors, there has not been an appropriate definition could be arrived at and each researcher(s) has had their own definitions. Though CE was defined in early 2000, a more vivid definitions were contributed, such as , *'psychological condition resulted from interactive and co creative consumer interaction '*, (Brodie et.al, 2009) *'behavioral manifestation beyond transactions but by motivational' drivers* (Van Doorn, 2010), *'customer's cognitive, emotional and behavioral aspects'* (Hollebeek,2011b) *'psychological process that simulates the underlying mechanisms by which new customers of a service brand develop loyalty'* (Bowden, 2009a) are some of the most discussed definitions of customer engagement.

The various definitions by researchers are enumerated in Table 4

Table 4 : Customer engagement definitions

Definition	Author	Term
Customer engagement can be described as the action of customer's association with a company or brand, beyond a transaction, but derived from motivational drivers	Vandoorn (2010)	Customer engagement behavior (CEB)
The extent of a consumer's cognitive, emotional, and behavioral investment in specific brand encounters is referred to as customer brand engagement.	Hollebeek (2011b)	Customer brand engagement (CBE)
The customer's cognitive and emotive commitment to an active relationship with the brand, as personified by the website or other computer-mediated entities designed to transmit brand value	Mollen and Wilson (2010)	Consumer engagement
A psychological condition resulting from interactive, co-creative consumer interactions with a focal agent/object in focal service relationships	Brodie, Hollbeek, Juric&lllic (2011)	Customer engagement
The degree to which an individual participates in and is connected to the organization's offerings and activities, whether initiated by the customer or the organization itself.	Vivek et al(2012)	Customer engagement
A psychological process that simulates the underlying mechanisms by which new customers of a service brand develop loyalty, as well as the mechanisms by which repeat purchase customers of a service brand keep loyalty.	Bowden(2009a)	Customer engagement
The physical, cognitive, and emotional "presence" of a consumer in their connection with a service business.	Patterson et al.(2016)	Customer engagement
A state of being involved, occupied, fully absorbed, or engrossed in something that causes a certain attraction or repulsion force to be generated.	Higgins and Scholer (2009)	Engagement
An individual distinction representing customers' propensity includes major brands in their self-perception.	Sprott (2009)	Brand Engagement in self - concept
In focal service relationships, a psychological condition that arises as a result of collaborative, co-creative client interactions with a focal agent.	Brodie et al (2011)	Customer engagement
"Modes of Engagement" refer to the various approaches to persuasion.	Philips and Macquarirrie(2010)	Engagement in Advertising
"Community engagement" is a motivating experience that involves being connected to a certain medium.	Calder et al(2009)	Community engagement
The consumer's natural desire to communicate or cooperate with other members of the community is boosted when they identify with the brand community.	Algesheimer et al (2009)	Community engagement
Cognitive effort, or the amount of cognitive capacity used on a specific task, is a component of the audience engagement.	Scott and Craig-Lees (2010)	Audience engagement

4.4 Theories used

Many theories are used by various researchers to support their concepts, out of which the major theories used by researchers are the personal engagement theory (Kahn,1996), Social Exchange theory, G.Homans (1953), and Relationship-marketing theory were commonly used theories. However, (Vargo and Lusch ,2004) developed a new concept, Service – Dominant logic (S-D) Logic that explains why organizations, markets, and society are fundamentally concerned with the exchange of service and the application of competencies (knowledge and skills) for the advantage of a party. This concept opened a new door for research in Customer Engagement. Table 5 shows the various theories used for building the concepts by the researchers.

Table 5 :Theories used in Customer engagement studies

Theories used	Explanation of Theory	Authors
Relationship Marketing Theory	According to relationship-marketing theory, as a firm provides value to its customers, the strength of its relationship with them improves, enhancing customer retention.	Bowden (2009a), Brodie et al. (2011, 2013),Hollebeek (2011b), Vivek et al. (2012, 2014) and Cambra-Fierro et al. (2013, 2015)
Grounded Theory	Grounded theory (GT) is a research method concerned with the generation of theory, which is 'grounded' in data that have been systematically collected and analyzed. It is used to uncover such things as social relationships and behaviors of groups, known as social processes	Vivek et.al (2012)
Personal Engagement Theory	The harnessing of organization members' selves to their work roles; through engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances is how engagement is defined. (kahn1990)	V.Dutot (2013)
Social Exchange Theory	This theory attributes that the relationship between two people is created through a cost-benefit analysis process (originally adapted from George Homans (1953)	(Hollebeek (2011b) N. Sinha et al (2011), A.Javonrnik et.al (2012), S.Bitter(2014), Nammir (2012)
Service – Dominant (S-D) logic	The core concept of S-D logic is that humans use their skills to help others and gain reciprocally from the skills of others through service-for-service exchange. (Originally developed by Vargo and Lusch (2004)	Hollebeek (2011a), Brodie et al. (2011, 2013), Breidbach et al. (2014), Chathoth et al. (2014) and Vivek et al. (2014)
Solicitation of congruity Theory	According to congruity theory, to avoid cognitive dissonance, consumers would exhibit a positive attitude toward an object that they consider consistent with their current belief(s) in some important respect. Originally developed byOsgood and Tannenbaum's (1955)	CK Coursaris (2013)
Equity Theory	According to Equity theory, we tend to develop systems where resources can be equitably distributed among group members to maximize individual gains. Originally adapted from John Stacy J.Adams (1963)	Ashley (2011)
Reciprocity Theory	A reciprocal action is described as the specific behaviorto action that is seen as either kind or unkind, according to this notion. Originally developed by Armin and UrsFuschbacher (2000)	Cambra-Feirro et al (2015)
Uses and gratification theory	A method for figuring out why and how people actively seek out specific media to meet their demands Originally adapted from Elihu Katz et.al(1973)	V.Ahuja et.al (2010)
Regulatory Focus theory	A person pursues a goal while maintaining their own personal values and beliefs (Originally adapted from Higgins (1997)	Hollebeek and Chen (2014)

4.5 Development of Conceptual Framework

Many concepts were developed by researchers based on the behavioral aspects of the customers (Vivek et.al (2012). Though the initial concepts were focused on individuals and their relationships with the brand, later this was extended to the firms too. Van doorn(2010) built a conceptual model with behavior manifestations, Brodie et.al (2013). Kumar et Al (2010) developed the metrics to measure the customer engagement. Table 6 shows the various conceptual frame work contributions made by various researchers.

Table 6 :Details of studies on conceptual framework

Authors	Year	Contribution/Outcome	Type of Study	Segment	Cite s
Van Doorn et al	2010	Defines Customer Engagement as a behavioral manifestation beyond the customer transactions arising from motivational drivers. Also explains why Customer behaves in many ways	Conceptual	General	3177
RJ Brodie, LD Hollebeek, B Jurić...	2011	Developed a refined conceptual frame work for Customer Engagement, essential for Marketing and Service Management	Conceptual	General	3037

RJ Brodie, A Ilic, B Juric, L Hollebeek	2013	Revealed that engagement is a complex multidimensional activity that changes its intensity with a period.	Conceptual	Virtual Brand Community	2881
Hollebeek et al.	2014	Identified that Brand involvement as antecedent and Self-brand usage and brand usage intent as the consequences	Conceptual	Social Media	2875
SD Vivek, SE Beatty, RM Morgan	2012	Define Customer engagement as the intensity of customer participation on the organization's offerings. Also developed a model comprising the constructs such as: Cognitive, emotional, behavioral and social components	Conceptual	General	1829
CM Sashi	2012	Developed a model with connection, interaction, satisfaction, retention, loyalty, advocacy	Conceptual	Social Media	1560
JLH Bowden	2009a	A conceptual frame work was developed showing the relationship between the c	Conceptual	General	1516
Mollen and Wilson	2010	Reconciled that engagement is a loyal and effective commitment related to a personified website	Conceptual	Digital Marketing	1355
V Kumar, L Aksoy, B Donkers	2010	Proposes that CEV has four components: Customer Life Time Value (CLT), Customer Knowledge Value (CKV), Customer Influencer Value (CIV) and Customer Referral Value (CRV)	Conceptual	General	1336
L Hollebeek	2011a	A definition for CBE was developed. A conceptual framework with three constructs such as Immersion, Passion and activation was developed	Conceptual	General	1335
PC Verhoef, WJ Reinartz...	2010	Identifies that Customer Engagement is the most important parameter of Customer Management	Conceptual	General	1129
Verhoef et al	2010	Developed Conceptual framework relating the antecedents, impediments and consequences of Customer Engagement	Conceptual	General	1120
L Hollebeek	2011b	Developed a conceptual framework comprising activation, identification and absorption dimensions for brand engagement	Conceptual	General	1116
Calder et al.	2009	Identified Positive correlation between the Advertising effectiveness and Personal & Social Interactive Engagement	Conceptual	Digital Media	1086
E Jaakkola, M Alexander	2014	Empirically tested the positive relationship of customer engagement and OBE value creation. Introduces nine research propositions for further research	Conceptual	General	1013
L Dessart, C Veloutsou...	2015	Identified cognition, affect and behavior as the key dimension of online brand engagement	Conceptual	Online Brand Community (OBC)	917
EC Malthouse, M Haenlein, B Skiera, E Wege...	2013	Observed that social media positively affect the customer engagement with respect to acquisition, retention and termination	Conceptual	Social Media	829
A Pansari, V Kumar	2017	Developed a conceptual frame work with Satisfaction and emotion as the antecedents with tangible and intangible as consequences	Conceptual	General	783
MTPMB Tiago, JMC Veríssimo	2014	Found that there is a tremendous pressure for the firm to go for digital and social media marketing	Conceptual	Social Media	757
SJ Berman	2012	Article		Digital	688
THA Bijmolt, PSH Leeflang, F Block...	2010	Developed a model to analyze the customer acquisition, development and retention	Conceptual	General	550
R Rishika, A Kumar, R Janakiraman...	2013	showed that customer participation in social media efforts leads to an increase in frequency of customer visits	Conceptual	Social Media	541
SD Vivek, SE Beatty, V Dalela...	2014	Proposes a Three Dimensional View of Customer Engagement such as conscious attention, Enthused participation and Social Connection	Conceptual	General (Metric)	478
Hollebeek and Chen	2014	Developed a Conceptual model with negatively and positively valence customer engagement and its antecedents and consequences	Conceptual	General	420
LD Hollebeek	2013	Revealed the curvilinear relationship between CE/CV. Further, it was found that CV is greater than CE for hedonic products in a specific situation, compared to utilitarian brands	Conceptual	General	290
LD Hollebeek, K Macky	2019	Derived fundamental propositions(FP) and a conceptual model encompassing the DCM and Customer Engagement, Trust and Value	Conceptual	General	201
E Maslowska, EC Malthouse...	2016	A conceptual model created with brand actions, other actors, customer brand experience, shopping behavior, brand consumption and brand dialog behavior.	Conceptual	General	199
EM Payne, JW Peltier, VA Barger	2017	Revealed the importance of IMC in an Omni channel customer engagement	Conceptual	Digital (OBC)	198
V Kumar, B Rajan, S Gupta, I DallaPozza	2019	Developed a framework facilitating the customer engagement service (CES in a service dominant logic	Conceptual	General	154

Angeles Oviedo _Garcia	2014	Developed a metric for customer engagement on Facebook	Conceptual	Online (Facebook)	132
Ashley and Tuten	2015	Confirms the importance of contents, frequent updates and incentive for participation influence the brand engagement	Conceptual	General	127
A Dovaliene, A Masiulyte, Z Piligrimiene	2015	Confirmed that there is a strong positive correlation between customer engagement, perceived value and satisfaction. Where as cognitive factors do not much impact on the perceived value and satisfaction	Conceptual	Digital (Mobile App)	106
SK Roy, V Shekhar, WM Lassar, T Chen	2017	Study indicated that customer engagement has a direct relationship with stickiness and indirect relation with value co-creation	Conceptual	General (CEB)	97
Franzak et al.	2014	Developed a conceptual model indicating the relation of Customer engagement with two antecedents: Design benefit and consumer emotions	Conceptual	General	93
RJ Brodie, JA Fehrer, E Jaakkola...	2019	Conceptualized a model of Actor- Actor, as Actor Engagement	Conceptual	General	84
SK Roy, MS Balaji, G Soutar, WM Lassar...	2018	Enlightened the importance of Integrated Marketing Communication in an Omni Channel context	Conceptual	General (CEB)	82
J Doorn	2011	Proposed Five Fundamental propositions that explain the underlying factors of customer engagement in a social media context.	Conceptual	General	81
A Javornik, A Mandelli	2012	Revealed that customers are unwilling to engage with FMCG unless it has a unique advantage	Article		79
Banyte et al.	2014	A conceptual model was developed indicating the relations of Customer Engagement with Value creation and loyalty	Conceptual	General	76
S Gupta, A Pansari, V Kumar	2018	introduced the concept of Global Customer Engagement and the cultural and behavioral aspects to help the marketers formulate global strategies	Conceptual	General	66
Kaltcheva et al	2014	Conceptual model explaining the influence of customer relation models, schemata and scripts	Conceptual	General	63
LD Hollebeek	2018	A conceptual model with individual cultural traits on customer engagement developed	Conceptual	General	62
V Dutot	2013	Editorial	Conceptual	Digital (CRM)	61
M Meire, K Hewett, M Ballings, V Kumar...	2019	Results showed that the marketers can influence the sentiments of the customer in a digital environment	Conceptual	General	54
M Alexander, E Jaakkola	2015	Book Chapter	Conceptual	General	53
R Kuvykaite, Z Piligrimiene	2014	Created a conceptual model of customer engagement that enhances the brand equity and value creation	Conceptual	General	49
M Christofi, D Vrontis, E Leonidou...	2018	conceptualized the role of CE in a CRM campaign	Conceptual	General	48
R Kuvykaitė, A Tarutė	2015	Identified the most common dimension of Customer Engagement	Conceptual	General	42
DSS Nammir, BM Marine, AM Ali	2012	Relevance of Customer Engagement on relationship quality and relationship performance established	Conceptual	General	40
E Jaakkola, L Aarikka-Stenroos	2019	Revealed the role of customer referencing and value creation in a networking context	Conceptual	General	36
Cambra- Fierro	2015	Empirically confirmed that better service handling increases the customer satisfaction and engagement	Conceptual	General(Service)	29
M Bergel, C Brock	2019	Showed that Engaged customers show a more positive attitude leading to better customer loyalty	Conceptual	General	25
E Abdul-Ghani, KF Hyde, R Marshall	2019	Developed a Conceptual model indicating the relation of Customer to Customer Relations with Customer Value	Conceptual	Digital (C2C)	23
M Bergel, P Frank, C Brock	2019	Observed that higher the customer engagement, higher the loyalty	Conceptual	General	19
SD Vivek, SE Beatty, M Hazod	2018	Identified the various dimensions of Customer Engagement	Conceptual	General	18
A Singh, GS Pathak	2020	Proposed a Customer Engagement model in CRM context	Conceptual	Digital	4
Chang Tang Chiang	2020	Study found that interaction with social members (social issues) mediates the association from social media (technical issues) to continuance intention.	Conceptual	Digital	4
DKX Do, K Rahman, LJ Robinson	2019	Conceptual frame work developed, which suggests that Customer-perceived justice and a negative disconfirmation lead to a negative customer engagement	Conceptual	General	4

4.6 Empirical Studies

The extant of literature shows that many empirical studies have been conducted on customer /consumer engagement. Factually, most of the empirical studies have been conducted after the digital revolution of the web. This could be justified since, the engagement of customers is widely possible in a digital platform than traditional way of engaging customers irrespective of any region. The empirical study on internet was initially published by (Sawhney et.al,2005) revealing the correlation of the production innovation in the internet platform. Subsequently, many studies were conducted by (Ahuja et.al, 2011) on customer relationship management, antecedents and consequences .Gummerus et.al argued that Customer Engagement need to be split in to Community engaged behavior (CEB) and Transaction Engaged Behavior (TEB). Table 7 shows the various contributions as a result of empirical studies.

Table 7: Details of empirical studies conducted on Customer Engagement

Authors	Year	Contribution / Outcome	Type of Study	Segment	Cites
SC Chu, Y Kim	2011	Antecedents such as Tie strength, homophile, trust, normative and informational interpersonal influence affect the eWOMbehavior	Empirical	Social Media (eWOM)	2457
M Sawhney, G Verona, E Prandelli	2005	Internet platform has a high impact on the Product Innovation	Empirical	Digital (Internet Platform)	1705
C Ashley, T Tuten	2014	Revealed the importance of frequency updates of the contents and incentives	Empirical	Digital	1227
J Gummerus, V Liljander, E women...	2012	Divided CE to Community Engaged Behavior (CEB) and Transaction Engagement Behavior (TEB)	Empirical	Social Media (Facebook)	1096
Gummerus et al.	2012	Customer Engagement was split in to Community Engagement Behavior (CEB) and Transaction Engagement Behavior (TBE) apart from three relationship benefits such as Social Benefits, Economic Benefits and Entertainment Benefits	Empirical	Social Media (Facebook)	1091
Sprott et al.	2009	Observed that higher the BESC, higher the brand loyalty and lesser price and Time sensitive	Empirical	General	890
J Wirtz, A Den Ambtman, J Bloemer...	2013	A conceptual frame work developed with four dimensions: Brand Orientation, Internet Use, Funding and Governance. Also identified three antecedents : Brand related, social and functional)	Literature Review	Online (OBC)	723
CM Harmeling, JW Moffett, MJ Arnold...	2017	Literature Review		General	503
Tsai and Men	2013	Factors identified Parasocial interaction and community identification has a significant relation for brand page retention factors. Whereas, Perceived credibility factors did not show a high relation.	Empirical	Social Media	501
WHS Tsai, LR Men	2013	confirmed that the relationship-oriented factors play a significant role in inducing social setup	Empirical	Social Media	498
NJ De Vries, J Carlson	2014	Identified four factors influencing social media engagement are Usage Intensity, social value, brand strength influence, Co-creation value	Empirical	Social Media (Facebook)	359
L Dessart, C Veloutsou...	2016	validated the importance of customer engagement in the social media	Empirical	Digital (OBC)	341
M Zhang, L Guo, M Hu, W Liu	2017	Revealed the importance of customer engagement, value creation and stickiness	Empirical	Social Media	330
Gambetti et al.	2012	Identified that CBE is a dynamic and process-based concept depending on the brand capability	Empirical	General	329
Dwivedi	2015	Defined brand engagement as the positive, fulfilling and brand used state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication and absorption	Empirical	Digital (Mobile App)	321
Breidbach	2014	Develop the " Engagement Ecosystem "	Empirical	Digital	266
Ashley et al.	2011	Identified that the perception of inconvenience and anticipated benefits influences the Relationship Program Receptiveness(RPR)	Empirical	General	262
R Guesalaga	2016	Developed model and empirically tested the various hypotheses of customer engagement	Empirical	Social Media	237

P Harrigan, U Evers, MP Miles, T Daly	2018	Validated the previous CE parameters	Empirical	Digital	196
V Ahuja, Y Medury	2010	Organizational, Promotional and relational content typologies could create enhanced consumer engagement	Empirical	Digital (eCRM)	184
TKH Chan, X Zheng, CMK Cheung, MKO Lee...	2014	Article	Empirical	Online (OBE)	179
R Thakur	2016	Conceptual model developed to measure the engagement of the mobile devices	Empirical	Digital (Mobile App)	177
KKF So, C King, BA Sparks, Y Wang...	2016	Article	Empirical	Digital (Service Brand)	165
J Carlson, M Rahman, R Voola...	2018	Empirical Study on the design of brand pages on online including customer and value perceptions	Empirical	Social Media	155
W Kunz, L Aksoy, Y Bart, K Heinonen...	2017	Suggested the importance of data driven customer engagement	Empirical	Digital	155
JU Islam, Z Rahman, LD Hollebeek	2018	Result showed that Value Congruity and Self-brand congruity positively influence the customer engagement on brand loyalty	Empirical	Online (OBC)	153
LD Hollebeek, J Conduit, RJ Brodie	2016	Customer engagement and its dimensions (Editorial)			145
A Tarute, S Nikou, R Gatautis	2017	Found that design of pages and the quality of information has a high correlation on the customer engagement through mobile apps	Empirical	Mobile (App)	133
Verhagen et al	2015	Developed a model relating characteristics of Virtual Environment, perceived benefits of using virtual environment and customer engagement	Empirical	Digital (Computers)	121
JU Islam, Z Rahman	2016	Revealed that Brand love and brand image have significant influence on customer engagement	Empirical	General (Fashion)	113
W Tafesse	2016	Research Documentation on Experiential model of Customer Engagement in social media	Empirical	Social Media	113
L Liu, MKO Lee, R Liu, J Chen	2018	Empirically proved that customer to Customer trust and Customer to Marketer trust have a significant correlation with the customer engagement	Empirical	Social Media	112
G Greve	2014	A conceptual of model with antecedents and consequences of customer engagement were first developed then validated the same through an empirical test	Empirical	Social Media	107
C Giannakis-Bompolis, C Boutsouki	2014	Reveals the various parameters influencing the online community.	Empirical	Social Media (Greek Bank)	95
M Husnain, A Toor	2017	Confirmed that the social networking marketing is significantly influence the customer purchase intention	Empirical	Social Media	92
ZWY Lee, TKH Chan, AYL Chong...	2019	Observed that channel integration quality has a significant association in Omni channel marketing	Empirical	Digital	90
V Viswanathan, LD Hollebeek...	2017	Revealed the significant connection between the mobile technology and the purchase behavior	Empirical	Digital (Mobile Technology)	85
FJ Martínez-López, R Anaya-Sánchez...	2017	Confirmed that engagement largely influences the customer's participation in the community.	Empirical	Online (OBC)	84
JU Islam, LD Hollebeek, Z Rahman, I Khan...	2019	Revealed a positive effect of customer engagement on service quality and is more in women than men	Empirical	General	84
R Dolan, J Conduit, C Frethey-Bentham...	2019	Revealed the distinct effect of rational and emotional appeals of Social Media Engagement	Empirical	Social Media	76
T Gong	2018	Revealed that cultural value orientation has direct relation with customer brand engagement behavior	Empirical	Digital (CEB)	71
CK Coursaris, W Van Osch, BA Balogh	2013	Developed a model with a new model with new typology that fits the CE in emerging social media perspective	Empirical	Social Media	65
Ž Piligrimienė, A Dovalienė...	2015	Techniques of customer engagement in value co-creation including gasification	Empirical	Digital (Facebook)	65

Cambra-Fierro	2013	revealed that there is high positive connection of Customer loyalty and positive word of mouth	Empirical	Conventional	63
AW Eigenraam, J Eelen, A Van Lin...	2018	Provided the various factors for managing the digital customer engagement	Empirical	Online	63
S Jayasingh, R Venkatesh	2015	Developed a model that relates the various factors affecting the customer engagement in brand pages (Facebook)	Empirical	Digital (Facebook)	59
N Barhemmati, A Ahmad	2015	Revealed the relationship between customer engagement, networking sites and purchase behavior as an outcome of it	Empirical	Social Media	59
JA Fehrer, H Woratschek, CC Germelmann	2018	Showed that for dyadic action between a customer and the brand, an incentive is required	Empirical	General	58
Y Gvili, S Levy	2018	Developed a conceptual frame with eWOM as the second-order Construct	Empirical	Social Media	55
K Heinonen	2018	Reveals that the negative or positive cognitive, behavioral and emotional factors affect the customer engagement	Empirical	General	53
N Sinha, V Ahuja, Y Medury	2011	Developed an experiment to measure the Customer Brand Knowledge, that positively correlated the Customer Engagement	Empirical	Digital (internet corporate blog)	52
T Carter	2008	Findings showed retained customers are more profitable than the new customers and Customer loyalty is important for retention	Empirical	General	50
S Bitter, S Grabner-Kräuter...	2014	found that the self-brand relationship and interaction with friends influence the Customer Engagement Behavior	Empirical	Social Media (Facebook)	45
CM Sashi, G Brynildsen, A Bilgihan	2019	found that retention effort and calculative commitment of customers as the most important factors influencing customer advocacy	Empirical	Social Media	40
R Thakur	2019	Found a higher degree of satisfaction for the people with a higher degree of customer engagement.	Empirical	Digital	36
P Parihar, J Dawra, V Sahay	2019	Reveals that the dimensions of involvement drive engagement differently	Empirical	General	32
CT Chiang, CF Wei, KR Parker...	2017	Empirically tested that Customer Engagement learning leads to satisfaction and then Customer Engagement behavior	Empirical	Social Media	31
D Gligor, S Bozkurt, I Russo	2019	Identifies that the parameters do positively influence the Online Customer Engagement	Empirical	Social Media	30
C Prentice, X Wang, X Lin	2018	Based on the expectancy theory, customer-perceived benefits were proposed as the causes for this relationship	Empirical	General	30
L Liu, R Liu, M Lee, J Chen	2019	Identified that recognition, community identification and self-efficacy are positively correlated with the SMBC	Empirical	Social Media	28
R Hussein, S Hassan	2017	Behavioral, emotional traits, cognitive and social Customer Engagement have higher correlation	Empirical	Social Media	27
A Dovaliene, Z Piligrimienė, A Masiulyte	2016	Confirms that Cognitive, behavior and emotional factors have a significant relationship in engagement creation	Empirical	Digital (Mobile App)	25
F de Oliveira Santini, WJ Ladeira, DC Pinto...	2020	found that satisfaction is the most important parameter affecting the customer engagement in social media	Empirical	Social Media (Meta Analysis)	24
J UI Islam, Z Rahman	2017	Information quality and virtual interactivity high level of influence on engaging the brand community	Empirical	Social Media (Facebook)	24
VM Lima, HAR Irigaray, C Lourenco	2019	empirically confirmed the process and sub processes of customer engagement	Empirical	Social Media	22
J Fromm, C Butler, C Dickey	2015	Conceptualized a model for engaging the Millennial Customers in a Social Media set up	Empirical	Social Media	22
J Marbach, C Lakes, D Nunan, Y Ekinci	2019	Findings showed that personality traits such as extraversion, openness to experiences and altruism do correlate positively with Online OCE	Empirical	Online (OBC)	21
A Lujja, FZ Özata	2017	Revealed that emotional and behavioral engagement dimension has high significance on brand loyalty. Emotional engagement for satisfaction; cognitive and	Empirical	Social Media (Facebook)	16

		behavioral engagement for commitment ; behavioral and emotional engagement for trust			
IP Chiang, SH Lo, LH Wang	2017	Results showed that social ties have high significant. And in general, Advertisement has high impact on the positive engagement	Empirical	Social Media (Advertising)	16
MHW Ho, HFL Chung	2020	Empirically tested that the mobile app engagement positively influences the customer engagement on engagement brand value, engagement on brand and equity relation ship	Empirical	Digital (Mobile App)	14
T Wang, FY Lee	2020	A conceptual frame work with customer initiated factors such as advice seeking, self-image expression as antecedents and Brand intimacy as consequences	Empirical	Social Media	14
J Demmers, JWJ Weltevreden...	2020	Observed that higher degree of activation in the brand page post is highly associated with high degree of engagement in the pre and post consumption stage but not in the consumption stage	Empirical	Social Media (Facebook)	12
S Quach, W Shao, M Ross, P Thaichon	2019	Found that as participation in the social media increases, the co- creation value is decreased. Extrinsic value was found to be a mediating factor between CE and customer participation	Empirical	Social Media	8
C Connell, R Marciniak, LI Carey...	2019	Observed that the product related environment cues drive CE in websites	Empirical	Digital (Website)	8
C Dhaoui, CM Webster	2021	Proposed as to how marketers can stimulate positive engagement	Empirical	Social Media (Facebook)	7
J Singh, S Nambisan, RG Bridge...	2020	Developed a conceptual framework that integrates service interaction space, Learning and Coordination, one voice strategy	Empirical	Digital	5
W Messner	2020	Revealed that highly engaged customer shows more interactions and more responses in a social media setting	Empirical	General (Hotel Pages)	1

4.7 Customer Engagement of Millennials

Millennials are those who are born between 1984 and 1994. The characteristics of millennials are largely different from the generation X (S.Raghavan and Ramesh Pai, 2021) . A few characteristics that separate from generation X are as follows :

- a. High technical exposure
- b. Highly demanding, impatient and choosy
- c. Seek quick solutions
- d. Socially connected
- e. Creative and free thinking
- f. Curious to know more and learn

Millennials make up 1.8 billion (23 percent) of the world's population and 426 million (36 percent) of India's. According to the survey, there haven't been enough conceptual or empirical studies on this cohort. Given the characteristics of millennials, it is critical to perform thorough research to engage, retain, and establish brand trust and loyalty. It has been observed that most scholarly publications have only been published in the recent year. Table 8 shows the scholarly papers published in top journals as of now.

Table 8 :Studies on Customer Engagement in Digital and Social media

Authors	Year	Type of Study	Area	Key Contribution/Findings
R Dolan, J Conduit, C Frethey-Bentham...	2019	Empirical	Social Media	Revealed the distinct effect of rational and emotional appeals of Social Media Engagement
T McCorkindale, MW DiStaso, HF Sisco	2013	Conceptual	Social Media (Millennials)	Explored the various aspects of customer engagement of Millennials
J Fromm, C Butler, C Dickey	2015	Conceptual	Social Media (Millennials)	Conceptualized a model for engaging the Millennial Customers in a Social Media set up
CM Harmeling, JW Moffett, MJ Arnold...	2017	Literature review	Social Media	
G Dash, K Kiefer, J Paul	2021	Conceptual	Digital (Millennials)	Brand image and Brand equity play an important role in engaging the millennials

5. DISCUSSION AND RESEARCH GAPS

From the extensive review, we observe that studies on customer engagement are still on premature stage and needs more investigations to reach a consensus on the concepts, fundamental propositions and the factors driving customer engagement, especially in the wake of

digitalization of marketing. There also need to be more research on the socio-cultural-psycho issues of the customers who tend to influence on the customer engagement depending on the regional locations. Very few studies have been conducted on the gender age especially the millennium customers whose characteristics widely different from the generation X, who are not as tech-savvy as the millennials. After the survey of the literature, the following research gaps have been identified

- a. Conceptual clarity on the various constructs that affect customer engagement , which can be generalized across the heterogeneous nature of the brand communities
- b. Further studies on the demographic characteristics that influence the customer engagement in digital media
- c. Determinants of customer engagement of millennials in a digital environment
- d. Continued studies on marketing technology , which continuously innovate the brand – customer interactions and its influence on customer engagement
- e. Most of the empirical studies were conducted only conducted in foreign countries, whereas hardly any quality studies were conducted on Indian customers.

6. LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

In spite of extensive digging of available literature, this paper has limitations. Firstly, all the papers were not free access papers. Hence this survey had to depend on working papers. Some cases, authors had to depend on abstracts due to which the full reading of methodologies could not be read. Secondly, the number of searches had limitations considering the longer length of the paper. Some good scholarly paper would have missed due to this.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Though customer retention has become gained prime importance among both practitioners and scholars, the extant literature prominently discussed for the last 16years shows that there has been a lack of consensus on the definition and the conceptual framework till date. Customer engagement has proved its essentiality, especially in the fast changing scenario of social and other media. Millennials customers tend to influence the customer engagement proposition much larger way owing to their general characteristics which cannot be ignored by any researchers as this cohort forms a substantial business potential. Hence, further studies on this group would be very much helpful for the marketers especially in the quick changing scenario of digital marketing.

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